

However, the selectivity is increased by the addition of surfactants.

Fig. 1. Effect of SDS concentration on R_f value of α -naphthol in various concentration of NaCl: (O) NaCl, (Δ) 2, ($\square$) 4, ($\times$) 6, ($\bullet$) 8 and ($\blacktriangle$) 10 $mM L^{-1}$ SDS.

The chromatography of phenol in these systems show differential selectivity which gives the differentiation of the R_f values, as a result the separation of isomeric phenols, e.g. *o*-nitrophenol from *p*-nitrophenol has been achieved. Various other important separations (binary and ternary) have been achieved in about 0.5 h using 8% propanol with 8 $mM L^{-1}$ SDS system as mobile phase.

The separations are quick and distinct zones are obtained on the paper (Fig. 2). The results show that a variety of aqueous micellar systems can be applied as mobile phase for interested separations.

Fig. 2. Separations achieved in 8 $mM L^{-1}$ SDS: (Ia) phloroglucinol, (Ib) α -naphthol, (IIa) picric acid, (IIb) 2,4-dinitrophenol, (IIIa) *p*-nitrophenol, (IIIb) *o*-nitrophenol, (IVa) picric acid, (IVb) 2,4-dinitrophenol and (IVc) *o*-nitrophenol.

Acknowledgement

Financial support of U.G.C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged. Thanks are also due to Professor W. Rahman, for facilities.

Reference

- W. L. HINZE in "Solution Chemistry of Surfactants", ed. K. L. MITTAL, Plenum Press, New York, 1979, Vol. 1, p. 79.

Cycloalkanes. Part-IV. Friedel-Crafts Condensation of *cis*-Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic Acid Anhydride with Aromatic Compounds and Synthesis of Simple and Substituted 2,3-Tetramethylene-5,6-benzcyclohexanes

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Manuscript received 23 October 1979, revised 15 December 1980, accepted 2 December 1985

THE Friedel and Crafts condensation between phthalic anhydride and simple, substituted and polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons has been reported^{1,2} in a bid to synthesise anthracene derivatives. However, no attempts have so far been made to condense *cis*-cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride with aromatic hydrocarbons under Friedel-Crafts reaction conditions. We now report here the synthesis of simple and substituted 2,3-tetramethylene-5,6-benzcyclohexanes. The anhydride of *cis*-cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid was

condensed separately with benzene, toluene and anisole in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give the corresponding 2-arylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acids (1a-c) which were characterised by ir and tlc. These acids when reduced by Wolff-Kishner method³ gave the corresponding 2-aryl-cyclohexane-1-carboxylic acids (2a-c) which were then converted into their chlorides by reaction with thionyl chloride. These acid chlorides when subjected to internal Friedel-Crafts reaction⁴ furnished the corresponding cyclic ketones (3a-c) which on subsequent Wolff-Kishner reduction yielded the desired hydrocarbons (4a-c) (Table 1).

TABLE 1

Compd no.	Aroyl	M.p. °C	Yield %	2,4-DNP M.p., °C	Mol formula	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
							C	H
2-Aroylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid								
1a	Benzoyl	131-2	91.0	162	$C_{14}H_{18}O_2$	1 705 (C=O) 1 695 (C=O) 3 400 - 2 900 (OH)	72.60 (72.41)	7.24 (6.90)
1b	4'-Methylbenzoyl	103-4	91.8	145	$C_{15}H_{18}O_2$	1 700 (C=O) 1 690 (C=O) 3 300 - 2 850 (OH)	73.50 (73.17)	7.36 (7.32)
1c	4'-Methoxybenzoyl	105	54.7	100	$C_{15}H_{18}O_2$	1 700 (C=O) 1 685 (C=O) 3 400 - 2 850 (OH)	68.46 (68.70)	6.51 (6.87)
2-Arylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid								
2a	Benzyl	97	60.9		$C_{14}H_{18}O_2$	1 705 (C=O) 3 400 - 2 900 (OH)	77.42 (77.06)	8.51 (8.26)
2b	4'-Methylbenzyl	122	60.7		$C_{15}H_{20}O_2$	1 700 (C=O) 3 300 - 2 850 (OH)	77.66 (77.59)	8.58 (8.62)
2c	4'-Methoxybenzyl	195	60.8		$C_{15}H_{20}O_2$	1 700 (C=O) 3 400 - 2 800 (OH)	72.78 (72.58)	8.16 (8.06)
2,3-Tetramethylene-substituted-5,6-benzcyclohexan-1-one								
3a	-	80	88.2	92	$C_{14}H_{18}O$	1 700	84.39 (84.00)	8.25 (8.00)
3b	2'-Methyl	86	84.3	115	$C_{15}H_{18}O$	1 690	84.36 (84.11)	8.40 (8.41)
3c	2'-Methoxy	90	83.3	119-20	$C_{15}H_{18}O_2$	1 690	78.43 (78.26)	7.56 (7.83)
2,3-Tetramethylene-substituted-5,6-benzcyclohexane								
4a	-	59-60	90.5		$C_{14}H_{18}$		90.54 (90.32)	9.45 (9.68)
4b	2'-Methyl	126	90.3		$C_{15}H_{20}$		90.05 (90.00)	9.94 (10.00)
4c	2'-Methoxy	77-8	79.1		$C_{15}H_{20}O$		83.64 (83.33)	9.55 (9.26)

It was further observed that the condensation of *cis*-cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride with benzene and toluene was carried out using the same medium as solvent and the keto acids (1a and b) were obtained in about 91% yield. When anisole was condensed under similar conditions poor yields of the keto acid was obtained. However, the keto acid (1c) was obtained in improved yields when anisole was condensed with the anhydride using nitrobenzene as the medium.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infra-red spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Carl Zeiss, Jena Specord 1R-75 spectrophotometer.

General procedure :

2-Aroylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid : *cis*-Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (0.064 mol) was dissolved in dry aromatic hydrocarbon (42 ml) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.128 mol) was added in small lots with frequent shaking. After storing the red coloured solution overnight,

the complex was decomposed with ice-cold hydrochloric acid. Excess of the aromatic hydrocarbon was removed by steam distillation, the product extracted with ether, washed, dried and ether recovered. Pure keto acid was obtained on crystallisation from benzene.

2-Arylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid : The keto acid (0.02 mol) was dissolved in diethylene glycol (40 ml), potassium hydroxide (0.08 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (3.7 ml, 80%) were added and the mixture refluxed at 130-140° for 1 h. The condenser was then removed and the internal temperature was slowly raised to 190-5°. The condenser was replaced and the mixture refluxed for further 3 h at this temperature. The contents were then cooled, acidified with hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, washed, dried and ether recovered. 2-Arylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid was obtained on crystallisation from benzene.

2,3-Tetramethylene-substituted-5,6-benzcyclohexane-1-one : To dry benzene (48 ml) reduced acid (0.018 mol) and thionyl chloride (9.6 ml) were added and the mixture refluxed for 3 h. After

removal of excess of thionyl chloride and benzene under reduced pressure, carbon disulphide (48 ml) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.018 mol) were added to the residue and the mixture refluxed for further 3 h and then stored overnight at room temperature. Carbon disulphide was then removed and the complex hydrolysed with ice-cold hydrochloric acid. The product was then extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was successively washed with water, dilute hydrochloric acid, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and finally with water, dried and chloroform recovered. Pure cyclic ketone was obtained on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether.

2,3-Tetramethylene-substituted-5,6-benzocyclohexane: A mixture of cyclic ketone (0.012 mol), diethylene glycol (20 ml), potassium hydroxide (0.048 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (1.7 ml, 80%) was refluxed for 1 h at 130-140°. The condenser was then removed and the internal temperature was slowly raised to 190-5°. The condenser was replaced again and the mixture refluxed for further 3 h. The contents were cooled, acidified with hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, washed, dried and ether recovered. The residue gave pure hydrocarbon on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether.

References

1. M. S. NEWMAN and C. D. McCLEARY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1540.
2. E. B. BARNET and N. R. CAMPBELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1031.
3. HUANG-MINLON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2487.
4. D. GINSBURG, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2361.

Preparation of Arylazo-bis-acetoximes

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Manuscript received 27 January 1984, revised 15 October 1985,
accepted 2 December 1985

IN an earlier communication, the preparation of ten new hydroxytriazenes was reported by the authors¹, in view of the importance of this class of reagents in analytical chemistry. The arylazo-bis-acetoximes also have the same chelating moiety as hydroxytriazenes.

Mai² discovered a group of substances conveniently called as arylazo-bis-oximes by coupling diazonium salts (1 mol) with ald- or ket-oximes

(2 mol). Bamberger³ proved that arylazo-bis-oxime have the hydroxytriazene skeleton. Elkins and Hunter⁴ reported preparation of six arylazo-bis-oximes and preparation of their nickel, cobalt, copper and iron complexes. Subsequently, Bhargava and Sogani⁵ reported the preparation of four arylazo-bis-oximes and screened for their utility in gravimetric analysis of copper and nickel.

The present communication describes the preparation of fourteen arylazo-bis-acetoximes and some of their physical properties. Qualitative spot test with α -naphthylamine has also been developed.

Experimental

Freshly prepared acetoxime (2 mol) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution and then cooled to 0° by adding some crushed ice to it and kept in ice-bath. A diazotised salt solution of the substituted anilines (1 mol) was then added slowly under mechanical stirring to this solution. The pH was always maintained at ~ 10 and the temperature during the entire course of addition being kept at 0°. The crude compounds obtained are mostly dark coloured. The crude product in each case was washed twice with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) to remove the coloured impurities, and recrystallised from ethanol-water mixture. The physical characteristics of the compounds are summarised in Table I.

Two methods for the spot test detection of hydroxytriazenes were reported by Purohit⁶. The basis of the first test is the formation of pink colour when an acetic acid solution of α -naphthylamine is added to an acetic acid solution of hydroxytriazenes. In the second method, addition of 2 to 5 drops of a saturated ethanolic solution of picric acid to either a pinch of solid hydroxytriazene or a drop of its ethanolic solution gives a pink or red colour of precipitate. Spot test detection of arylazo-bis-acetoxime series of compounds with α -naphthylamine has been developed for the first time. However, with picric acid these have failed to respond to the test.

One drop of arylazo-bis-acetoxime solution in acetic acid (0.001%, w/v) was treated in a small test tube with a drops of acetic acid solution (0.01% w/v) of α -naphthylamine. Pink or reddish brown colour developed immediately. Gentle warming of the test solution further intensified the colour. The test was performed with seventeen arylazo-bis-acetoxime compound. The results of the test are given in Table 1.

Discussion

Hydroxytriazenes are reported to exist in intramolecular hydrogen bonded form (III). This group of compounds have also been named as triazene oxide on the basis of possible existence of its tautomeric form (II).